

MAIN FACTORS TO DEVELOP COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES IN 5–6 GRADERS

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Annotation: This article highlights the concepts of competence and communicative competence and key factor which influence for the development of communicative competences of 5-6 graders. It also defines different factors such as individual, environmental, instructional.

Keywords: individual factors, environmental factors, instructional factors

Communicative competence is the ability to use language effectively in a variety of contexts. It includes the ability to understand and use language grammatically, to be aware of social and cultural rules of communication, and to be able to communicate effectively in different settings.

The development of communicative competence is a complex process that is influenced by a variety of factors, including:

• **Individual factors:**

◦ **Cognitive abilities:** Children with stronger cognitive abilities are better able to understand and use language effectively. This includes the ability to think critically, problem-solve, and reason.

◦ **Language skills:** Children with strong language skills are better able to communicate their ideas clearly and concisely. This includes the ability to use a variety of vocabulary and sentence structures and to understand the nuances of language.

◦ **Motivation:** Children who are motivated to communicate are more likely to take risks and practice their skills. This can be influenced by a number of factors, such as the child's interest in the topic, their relationship with the person they are communicating with, and their perceived competence as a communicator.

Personality: Some children are naturally more outgoing and talkative than others, which can give them an advantage in developing communicative competences. However, it is important to remember that everyone communicates differently, and there is no one "right" way to be a communicator.

• **Environmental factors:**

Socioeconomic status: Children from low-income families may have fewer opportunities to develop their communicative competences outside of school. This is due to a number of factors, such as limited access to quality childcare, fewer opportunities to participate in extracurricular activities, and less exposure to language models.

Family support: Parents and other family members can play a key role in supporting children's communicative development by providing them with opportunities to practice speaking and listening in a variety of contexts. This can include talking to their children about their day, reading to them, playing games that require communication, and encouraging them to interact with others.

Peer relationships: Children learn a lot about communication from their peers. Positive peer relationships can provide children with opportunities to practice their communication skills in a supportive environment.

School climate: A positive school climate can create a supportive environment for children to develop their communication skills. This includes a classroom environment where students feel safe and respected and where they are encouraged to share their ideas and opinions.

• **Instructional factors:**

Teacher quality: Teachers who are skilled in teaching communication can provide children with the opportunities and support they need to develop their communicative competences. This includes creating a classroom environment that is conducive to communication, using a variety of instructional strategies, and providing feedback to students on their communication skills.

Instructional strategies: Specific instructional strategies, such as cooperative learning, drama, and role-playing, can be effective for developing children's communicative competences. These strategies provide children with opportunities to practice their communication skills in a variety of contexts and with different audiences.

Classroom environment: A classroom environment that is conducive to communication, such as one that is safe, supportive, and respectful, can help children develop their communicative competences. This includes creating a classroom where students feel comfortable asking questions, sharing their ideas, and making mistakes.

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